

**Experience of Partial Discharge with IEC Type Testing and after Installation
Testing for extruded Cables**

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SUMMARY

Partial Discharge (PD) measurement methods are most important and preferred in testing of underground high voltage cables and they have received much attention in recent years. Apparent charge, partial discharge inception voltage as well as number and distribution of PD pulses are most important quantities for the determination of the insulation quality. This paper described experiences of PD measurements with AC resonant voltages in Extra High Voltage Research Centre (EHVRC) laboratory according to IEC standards and after installation test of installed XLPE HV and EHV single core underground cable systems. The paper outlines the difference between PD measurements performed on individual components in the laboratory and PD measurements performed on installed systems in the after installation with respect to magnitude calibration of PD pulses. Fact is that all the power cables are tested in the laboratory with the best methods and with calibrated PD measuring systems in the shielded room with high sensitivity; as a result the background noise level is less than 2 pC. A general principle of the insulation co-ordination and HV testing is that the applied test voltage simulates the stresses which occur during the operation of the HV apparatus. Successful measurements give fingerprint for further diagnostics during the service of the cable system. Tell now for after installation test, PD measurements are actually not required by IEC 60840 & IEC 62067, but the testing experience more than 12 years shows a population of extrude cable systems subjected to a combination of AC testing and PD measuring acceptance testing. This paper summarizes the experiences of on-site testing and the obtained results are compared with the IEC type tests. One important conclusion of this paper is modifications of IEC 60840 & IEC 62067 are required to evaluate the on-site after installation testing for extruded cables.

KEYWORDS

Partial Discharge, Conventional and Un-conventional, XLPE cable systems, Variable Frequency Tune Resonant Test

1. INTRODUCTION

Power cables are of great importance in power transmission and distribution systems. Joints and terminations are the basic accessories of the power cables. They are required to make connections between cable parts or to an electrical apparatus. The various aspects are considered while designing and installation of the cable terminations and joints because they must possess the same integrity as their associated cables while making the connection both all indoor and outdoor applications. High voltage tests should provide the information for decision whether a defect in the insulation is dangerous or not for the later operation. That means the failure mechanism during the HV test and the later operation should follow the same physical process. To accelerate this process, the test voltage is usually higher than the corresponding stress during operation. The most important stress of XLPE cable systems in service is the stress with the alternating voltage operation. If an on-site test is completed with a PD measurement, all the experience from the various on-site tests can be transferred to the factory tests. On the other hand, experience also shows that the after installation PD measurements by using frequency tuned resonant test systems gives high sensitivity and calibration is possible using PD calibrator on the cable terminations. Two different PD detection methods conventional and un-conventional are used for investigation. After laying tests a diagnostic measurement should detect faults and defects caused by transports and installation. Conventional IEC 60270 [1] PD detection is applied by using PD detector with high voltage series resonant at frequency 50 Hz continuous, and the another method un-conventional PD detection is applied by using PD detector with High Frequency Current Transformer (HFCT) sensor around earth wire or around the bar of cross bonding box for the long HV/EHV cables with variable frequency tuned resonant test system (20 Hz -300 Hz) have been gained in on-site test. Thus, partial discharge measurement is an important diagnostic tool. For un-conventional PD detection the distance of HFCT sensors from the PD source determine the attenuation of the high frequency PD pulses.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The entire experimental test presented was carried out in partial discharge measuring laboratory at the Extra High Voltage Research Center, and on-site measurements with variable frequency tune resonant test system. Partial discharges that occur in the test object will produce current or voltage pulses. In contrast to the well-established PD measuring method according to IEC 60270 the described system operates in the UHF frequency domain, hence the derived and evaluated output PD pulse magnitude is more or less a measure of the PD current amplitude and not for the apparent charge as defined in the above mentioned standard [2]. Conventional PD detection method is standardized method based on international standard IEC 60270. This method based on measurement of the charge displacement q , expressed in (pC), from the pulses which generated from partial discharge. In these PD measurements, 50Hz continuous AC voltage is used as an energizing method. The PD detector consists of several important components: regulator transformer, high voltage reactor, high voltage filter, coupling capacitor, digital universal measuring instrument and PD detector (TE 571). PD measurement is carried out in 2 minutes for each test voltage. During this period three quantities are recorded: the number of PD pulses, the maximum value of PD magnitudes and the average value of PD magnitudes [3]. The PD measurements have been carried out according to IEC 62067 for the XLPE cable sample 220 kV -1600 mm² with three different type of joints and two terminations (indoor and outdoor termination), cable sample

length required for type test approximately 35 meters as shown in Figure (1). AC offline test voltages according to IEC standards can be generated in two different ways:

- By a reactor with variable inductance and fixed excitation frequency, e.g. 50 or 60 Hz.
- By a reactor with fixed inductance and frequency-tuned voltage excitation.

Figure 1: XLPE cable sample 220 kV – 1x1200 mm² with accessories under type test according to IEC 62067

The partial discharge type test according to IEC 62067 [4] is carried out by the following sequence:

- a- Bending test and a partial discharge test at ambient temperature.
- b- Partial discharge tests after heating cycle voltage test:
 - At ambient temperature.
 - At high temperature.

The tests are performed in accordance with IEC 60885-3[5], the sensitivity being 5 pC or better. The test voltage is raised gradually to and held at $1.75 U_0$ for 10 seconds, and after that the applied voltage is slowly reduced to $1.5 U_0$ before measuring the cable system PD response. Calibration is done by injecting a short duration current pulse of known charge from the calibrator to the terminal of test object while the measuring system is de-energized. Calibration of PD measuring instrument is important factor to ensure that the PD measuring system is able to measure the PD magnitude properly. The apparent charge estimation must take into account the PD measurement system gain and the complex attenuation and dispersion experienced by a PD pulse originating from anywhere in the cable system.

The after installation testing of cables has to check the insulation condition after laying and assembly of cable systems, as well as ageing of cables and accessories, since the performance of the cable and accessories was tested during the type and routine tests. The after laying test of new cables fills the “quality assurance gap” between the type and routine tests of the cable at the manufacturer's site and the commissioning of the complete cable system on-site. After installation testing of EHV cable system is actually carried out by

alternating voltage of variable frequency tests according to two international standards cover after installation tests of extruded cable systems IEC 60840 and IEC 62067. Both IEC standards define, for the first time, identical requirements for the shape of suitable AC test voltage and for the time of its application: substantially sinusoidal waveform, frequency between 20 and 300 Hz and time of voltage application equal to 1 hour (at $1 U_0 / 24$ h) [4,6,7]. Both IEC standards offer line voltage testing ($1 U_0 / 24$ h) as an alternative procedure. Obviously, there is no need for an extra test voltage source.

Figure 2 Frequency tuned resonant test system (20 Hz- 300Hz)

3 FREQUENCY TUNED RESONANT OF VOLTAGE TEST

An AC Frequency Tuned Resonant system (ACRF) as given in Figure 2 (a,b) mainly consists of a reactor with fixed inductance (optionally with taps), the capacitive load (test object) and a control module with frequency converter unit. Resonance is reached by tuning the frequency of the converter unit. In series resonant circuit, the test voltage is a pure sinusoid, but its frequency depends on load capacitance, which varies between test objects. For a constant inductance L there is a minimum resonant frequency for a maximum load capacitance. The frequency increases with decreasing load capacitance. In addition to the test voltage, the maximum load capacitance and the acceptable frequency range are decisive design criteria for the fixed HV reactor of the ACRF test system. Resonant reactors can be combined in series or parallel connection to adapt to certain test parameters. The Extra High Voltage Research Centre (EHVRC) has a variable frequency test system (20 Hz to 300 Hz) with $4.28 \mu\text{F}$ maximum test capacitance which corresponds to cable length of 16.4 km at a cable capacitance of $0.26 \mu\text{F/km}$ for after installation tests carried out on 220 kV, XLPE cables. The variable frequency test system is used to improve cables performance by using up to date technology for On-site withstand tests of power cable systems. The tests are mainly performed to check the quality of the accessories and their assembling. Test frequency depending on load capacitance including basic load of test system. The resonant circuit must have both capacitance and inductance when the resonance occurs, the energy absorbed at any instant by one reactive element within the system. The control of test system searches for the resonant frequency automatically and the HV test is carried out at this frequency [8].

4 TEST RESULT AND EXPERINCE

A. PD measurements during type test:

Conventional PD detection based on IEC 60270 has been used many years as a standardized method for PD measurement. However, this method has a limitation when used in the field measurement due to relatively high level of ambient noise. The measurements are carried out to determine the PD level of 220 kV – XLPE cable during type test. The entire measurement are carried out using PD detector, model TE 571 in the EHVRC laboratory. PD measurement is done in 2 minutes for each test voltage. During this period three quantities are recorded: the number of PD pulses, the maximum value of PD magnitudes and the average value of PD magnitudes. The phase-position quantities $H_{qmax}(\varphi)$, $H_{qn}(\varphi)$ and $H_n(\varphi)$ are measured for the 220 kV cable termination and the display a 3-dimensional (3D) relationship between discharge magnitude, discharge intensity and phase angle the $H_n(\varphi, q)$ distribution is used. These three quantities are plotted as a function of phase angle of sinusoidal AC voltage. There are more discharge quantities in the positive half of power voltage cycle than that in negative half, and the number of discharges in the positive half is more than that in the negative half. From the discharge phase-position distribution, and this figure shows the PD quantities maximum discharge magnitude $q_{max}(t)$, and the number of pulses/second as observed during 2 minutes test time. The first PD measurement at ambient temperature recorded 7.5 pC as results bubbles in the oil termination and after oil degassing from termination recorded 2.8 pC as shown in Figures (3, 4).

Figure 3 Phase-position quantities $H_{qmax}(\varphi)$, $H_{qn}(\varphi)$, $H_n(\varphi)$, $H_n(\varphi, q)$ and 3D distribution processed for discharges before oil degassing from termination

Figure 4 Phase-position quantities $H_{qmax}(\varphi)$, $H_{qn}(\varphi)$, $H_n(\varphi)$, $H_n(\varphi, q)$ and 3D distribution processed for discharges after oil degassing from termination

B. PD measurements after installation

The most important stress of XLPE cable in service is the stress with the operational alternating voltage. Consequently the most favored on-site test voltage of power frequency, standardized for laboratory testing in the range from 45 to 50 Hz. But for on-site testing a larger frequency range is being discussed. The on-site testing of cables has to check the insulation condition after-laying and assembly of cable system, as well as ageing of cables and accessories, since the performance of the cables and accessories was tested during the type and routine tests. The after laying test of new cables fills the quality assurance gap between the type and routine tests of the cable at the manufactures site and the commissioning of the complete cable system on-site. During the assembly or repair of a cable system, defects of the cable sheath and misassembled of joints and terminations can occur [9]. Many years of experiences in testing and measuring HV/EHV cables with XLPE insulation and accessories having different lengths to determine the faulty joints, termination and cable defect. Therefore, the XLPE cables insulation was subjected to AC tests after assembling and at the same time partial discharge measurements were done on all accessories simultaneously for three-phase PD measurement on the relevant joint box would be possible, also the cross-bonding can be changed to straight-through connection, to minimize cross-talk between the three phases and to clearly distinguish between the three joint of one group. In this section same example of 230 kV – 1x1600 mm² cable consist of 10 km long XLPE cable circuit is divided into two sections by means of joints and it is terminated by composite three outdoor and three GIS sealing ends. Each phase is tested for 1 hour at 216 kV ac voltages (phase to ground voltage) at voltage frequency during the test 37.28 Hz and acquiring PD signals from HFCT sensors installed in the link boxes as given in Figure 5. Although each single cable and accessory is subject to routine tests at the manufacturer laboratory, transportation, cable laying and installation can lead to unnoticed defects. External damages due to cable laying are usually detected by DC testing of the over sheath. In consequence, after-installation tests of the insulation can focus on defects in cable accessories, e.g. interfacial problems, improper positioning, cuts or scratches, contaminations etc. Such defects do not necessarily lead to breakdown within testing time, bearing the risk of breakdowns later in service. Sensitive on-site PD measurements significantly reduce this risk [10, 11, and 12].

Figure 5 Measurement setup for PD detection using HFCT sensor

Partial discharge measurements carried out during HV tests, using a test sequence providing several increase of the voltage in steps of 50 kV and observing the PD pattern at each voltage level. At $U_0 = 127$ kV a PD-measurement recording during 1 minute is taken and afterwards increasing the voltage in further steps of 50 kV until 216 kV. At each step the measured PD value is recorded. Once reaching to 216kV, the applied voltage is left for 1 hour

and the partial discharge is recorded and measured, just before the 1 hour test period another recording of the PD measurement for 1 minute is carried out. While ramping the test voltage down, the PD measurement for 1 minute at $U_0 = 127$ kV is done. The test procedure is shown in Figure (6). PD sensors work based on detection of high frequency current pulses that occur during PD in the cable system. The PD pulses occur in very short time, the width and rise time of the pulses are in the nanosecond region. Consequently, PD pulses with energy frequency up to hundred MHz are generated. These PD pulses with travel through the cable earth conductor and finally can be recorded by the sensors. These types of sensor mostly used in practice due to the advantage that these sensors do not disrupt the normal configuration of the accessories and cable part. The results of on-site PD measurements for power cable system 230 kV – 1x1600 mm² by using High Frequency Current Transformer (HFCT) sensors placed in previous joint to the cable end permit us to discriminate what PD pulses are located at the cable end and the ones placed in the cable joint for approximately 10 km long installation included 17 joints / phase is shown in Figure (7). The variation of noise level which is experienced during all measurements resulting in higher external interference from ends of the cable, also corona effect caused by floating parts close to high voltage at the cables termination. Many times, experienced has been carried out for after installation testing according to IEC 62067 for cable system having different lengths to determine the faulty joints as shown in Figure (8)

Figure 6: Schematic application of PD measurements to confirm the non-destructiveness by using AC frequency tuned resonant system

Figure 7: On-site PD measurements of cable 230 kV – XLPE – 1x1600 mm² by using HFCT sensors for approx. 10 km

Figure 8 : Exampes for 230 kV joint failures

5. CONCLUSIONS

Two different PD detection methods conventional and un-conventional are used for investigation. After laying tests a diagnostic measurement should detect faults and defects caused by transports and installation. IEC standards defined, for the first time, identical requirements for the shape of suitable AC test voltage. For after installation tests, PD measurements are actually not required by IEC standards tell now, but the experiences of after installation tests recommended for the modifications of both IEC standards 60840 & 62067 are required to evualate the after installation tests for HV / EHV extruded cables. Partial discharge measurement is an important diagnostic tool. Ater installation tests a diagnostic measurement should defect faults and defects caused by transports and installation. Successful measurements give fingerprint for further diagnostics during the service of the cable system.

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